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1 **Response of cotton to irrigation, fertilization and plant density in a semi-arid region of Iran**

2

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4

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7

8

9 **Summary**

10 Fertilization and plant density are key factors in cotton yield, especially under conditions
11 of water shortage. We conducted a two years field experiment to investigate the nitrogen × PSB
12 bacteria synergic effect on photosynthesis and water relation of cotton under water stress
13 conditions and different plant densities. The experimental design was a 2⁵ factorial with five
14 factors I: Irrigation (moderate and restricted irrigation), N: Nitrogen (with and without nitrogen),
15 D: Plant density (low and high plant density), B: PSB bacteria (with and without incubation), P:
16 Phosphorus (with and without phosphorus). Results revealed that the ratio (Fv/Fm) did not
17 respond to restricted irrigation when N and B were consumed together, and one of these factors
18 was also enough to prevent the decline in the relative water content (RWC) under I_R conditions. P
19 had a reducing effect on RWC under I_R conditions, and its role in preventing LAI loss under
20 restricted irrigation condition did not result in the improvement of yield (GLY). I_R reduced RWC

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21 and GLY in low density plots without nitrogen consumption, but using N or higher plant density
22 was enough to prevent this decline. The results conclude that P can be replaced with B under I_R
23 conditions, and the synergic interaction of N×B can strongly reduce the effect of drought stress
24 on cotton yield in high plant density.

25 **Key words:** Irrigation, Fertilization, Plant Density, Chlorophyll fluorescence, Relative Water
26 Content, Cotton.

27 **Abbreviations:** N, Nitrogen; P, Phosphorus; B, PSB-bacteria; I, irrigation; RWC, Relative water
28 content; F_v/F_m, chlorophyll fluorescence; Chl: chlorophyll; GLY: grain and lint yield; N₀ and
29 N_H: without and with nitrogen consumption; P₀ and P_H: without and with phosphorus
30 consumption; B₀ and B_H: without and with PSB-bacteria incubation; I₀ and I_R: moderate and
31 restricted irrigation; D₀ and D_H: low and high plant density;

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41]

42 **Response of cotton to irrigation, fertilization and plant density in a semi-arid region of Iran**

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47

48 Running title: Fertilization and plant density of cotton under water shortage.

49

50 **Summary-**

51 Fertilization and plant density are key factors in cotton yield, especially under conditions

52 of water shortage. This research investigated the nitrogen × PSB bacteria synergic effect on

53 photosynthesis and water relation of cotton under water stress conditions and different plant

54 densities. The experimental design was a 2⁵ factorial with five factors I: Irrigation (moderate and

55 restricted irrigation), N: Nitrogen (with and without nitrogen), D: Plant density (low and high

56 plant density), B: PSB bacteria (with and without incubation), P: Phosphorus (with and without

57 phosphorus). Results revealed that the ratio (Fv/Fm) did not respond to restricted irrigation when

58 N and B were consumed together, and one of these factors was also enough to prevent the decline

59 in the relative water content (RWC) under I_R conditions. P had a reducing effect on RWC under

60 I_R conditions, and its role in preventing LAI loss under restricted irrigation condition did not

61 result in the improvement of yield (GLY). I_R reduced RWC and GLY in low density plots
62 without nitrogen consumption, but using N or higher plant density was enough to prevent this
63 decline. The results conclude that P can be replaced with B under I_R conditions, and the synergic
64 interaction of N×B can strongly reduce the effect of drought stress on cotton yield in high plant
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69 content; F_v/F_m , chlorophyll fluorescence; Chl: chlorophyll; GLY: grain and lint yield; N_0 and
70 N_H : without and with nitrogen consumption; P_0 and P_H : without and with phosphorus
71 consumption; B_0 and B_H : without and with PSB-bacteria incubation; I_0 and I_R : moderate and
72 restricted irrigation; D_0 and D_H : low and high plant density;

73

74 INTRODUCTION

75 Bio-fertilizer is still an unclear technology in organic farming because of inadequate
76 awareness about its use, benefits and disadvantages (Basu et al. 2017). Phosphorus precipitates
77 with calcium and magnesium ions in alkaline and saline soils of the semi-arid areas, and is not
78 mostly absorbable for root (Silva et al. 2014; Shen et al. 2011). So, PSB-bacteria in sunflower,
79 corn, cotton or other row crops is recommended to farmers as an organic way of introducing P
80 into low-input cropping systems in Iran and some other Mediterranean regions (Latati et al.

81 2017). The other problem is the very poor yield of cotton due to interspecific competition for
82 nitrogen, this show the importance of some nitrogen use to decrease competition between plants
83 for N and prevent cotton yield loss (Silva et al. 2014).

84 Row crops in higher plant density produce deeper roots than in low plant density, as
85 Shao et al. (2018) reported that root growth in maize was enhanced under high plant density.
86 Consequently, the competition between the plants in high plant density appears to be mainly for
87 nutrients (Li et al. 2019), especially nitrogen and phosphorus which have an uniform distribution
88 in the soil layers, rather than water, which is more available in the lower layers of the soil where
89 cotton roots can access (Estrada et al. 2015). Li et al. (2017) and Shi et al., (2016) reported that
90 an acceptable lint yield was achieved with nitrogen under high plant density, indicating the
91 interaction of fertilizer × plant density on cotton and maize yield. High density can reduce flower
92 and young bolls shedding in drought stress conditions, because at high densities, indicating
93 significant interaction of irrigation × plant density (Shi et al. 2016).

94 So, the objective of this study is testing the idea of whether consumption of N and PSB-
95 bacteria together and high plant density can alleviate the effect of water stress on cotton yield.

96 We hypothesis that PSB provides the phosphorus and if nitrogen is sufficiently available
97 through consumption of some nitrogen in high plant density conditions, then P-related
98 mechanisms such as better root system growth results to increased relative water content (RWC)
99 of the leaves and reduced chlorophyll fluorescence which ultimately prevents a significant
100 decrease in the yield of cotton under restricted irrigation.

101

102 **MATERIALS AND METHODS**

103 **Location and Plant material**

104 This experiment was carried out during the 2017 and 2018 growing seasons at Feizabad-
105 Iran (latitude: 34°54'N, longitude: 58°70'E) with the cotton cultivar “Varamin”. The growing
106 season was about 100 days in both years, beginning from May 22 to August 31. In Feizabad, the
107 temperature varied from 20°C to 38°C during the growing season and was rarely below 16°C or
108 above 41°C. There was no rainfall during this period in both years. The soil used was a
109 montmorillonite clay loam, low in total nitrogen (0.06 %), low in soluble potassium (257 ppm)
110 low in organic matter (0.6 %), low in absorbable phosphate (12 ppm), with a pH of 8.0 and Ec of
111 0.89 dS/m

112

113 **Treatments and experimental design**

114 The 2⁵ factorial experiment consisted of five factors (I: Irrigation, N: Nitrogen, D: Plant
115 density, B: PSB bacteria, P: Phosphorus), each with two levels with their combination. The levels
116 of experimental factors included the following: I_R, I_O: Optimal and restricted irrigation,
117 respectively; N₀, N_H: without and with nitrogen consumption, respectively (consumption of 133
118 kg ha⁻¹ urea fertilizer contains 48% pure nitrogen at seven weeks after sowing); D₅, D₁₀: plant
119 density of 5 and 10 plants per square meter respectively; B₀, B_H: without and with PSB bacteria
120 consumption, respectively (Incubation with 100 g ha⁻¹ PSB bacteria at two weeks after sowing);

121 P_0 , P_H : without and with phosphorus consumption, respectively (consumption of 133 kg ha^{-1}
122 triple superphosphate fertilizer contains 46% pure phosphorus at sowing). A subplot size of $6 \text{ m} \times$
123 3 m , having 6 rows of 6 m length was used.

124

125 **Irrigation Scheduling:**

126 Furrow irrigation with siphons was applied. Up to seven weeks after sowing, all the
127 experimental units were irrigated uniformly when the soil water content (SWC) reached $[\theta_{WP} +$
128 $75\% (\theta_{FC} - \theta_{WP})]$. After this stage, water content before irrigation in I_0 and I_R plots was $[\theta_{WP} +$
129 $75\% (\theta_{FC} - \theta_{WP})]$ and $[\theta_{WP} + 25\% (\theta_{FC} - \theta_{WP})]$, respectively. θ_{FC} and θ_{WP} were SWC at field
130 capacity. SWC was measured daily by using granular matrix sensors according to the method that
131 described in our previous research (Madani et al. 2010). The amount of irrigation during the
132 growing season was based on evapo-transpiration (ETP). Reference ETP (ETP_0) was measured
133 using class A evaporation pan. ETP_0 then multiplied by the water stress coefficient (Ks) and the
134 crop coefficient (Kc) to calculate the crop evapo-transpiration (ETPc). Ks values for different
135 soil water contents and Kc values for cotton at different growth stages is reported by FAO
136 irrigation and drainage-paper 56. (Allen et al. 1998). Net irrigation water requirement in
137 moderate irrigation (I_0) plots was 1250 mm (2017) – 1500 mm (2018), and in restricted irrigation
138 (I_R) plots was 970 mm (2017) – 1200 mm (2018).

139

140 **Measurements**

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141 Chlorophyll content was measured with “SPAD 502 Plus” chlorophyll meter. The ratio
142 Fv/Fm was measured with “Hansatech Pocket Pea” chlorophyll fluorimeter before and after
143 irrigation. These two traits were measured at the start of R2 and the end of R6 growth stages
144 which were in accordance with the 56th and 77th days after sowing, respectively. The following
145 formula was used to calculate the RWC (Barrs & Weatherley 1962):

146
$$\text{RWC (\%)} = [(W-DW) / (TW-DW)] \times 100,$$

147 Where,

148 W – Sample fresh weight of leaf disks (10 cm²).

149 TW – Sample turgid weight (hydrated to full turgidity for 3-4h at 20°C)

150 DW – Sample dry weight (dried at 80⁰C for 24h).

151 An area of 2 m² was harvested to estimate the yield.

152

153 **Data Analysis**

154 Statistical analyses were performed using the GLM procedure with SAS 9.3. Duncan’s
155 multiple range test was applied for mean separations when F values were significant.

156

157

158 **RESULTS** Chlorophyll content (Chl) did not respond to the treatments. Light and
159 dark-adapted Fv/Fm were measured before and after irrigation at different growth stages. Only
160 dark-adapted Fv/Fm values measured before the irrigation and at the beginning of reproductive

161 growth (R_2) were influenced by some experimental factors. The correlation of Fv/Fm with yield
162 (GLY) was significant in both years only under restricted irrigation (Table 1).

163 Based on the average of years, restricted irrigation (I_R) caused a 14.9% ($I_0=0.67$, $I_R=0.57$,
164 $LSD_{0.01}=0.03$) decrease in Fv/Fm. $I \times N \times P$ and $I \times N \times B$ interactions were significant on Fv/Fm in
165 both years (Table 1). Based on the average of years, Fv/Fm did not respond to I_R when N and P
166 were consumed together ($I_0N_HP_H=0.62$; $I_RN_HP_H=0.60$), while I_R resulted in a significant reduction
167 in Fv/Fm when P ($I_0N_HP_0=0.69$; $I_RN_HP_0=0.54$) or N ($I_0N_0P_H=0.69$; $I_RN_0P_H=0.56$) or both
168 ($I_0N_0P_0=0.68$; $I_RN_0P_0=0.59$) were not consumed (Fig. 1.A). A similar trend was observed when P
169 was replaced with PSB bacteria (B). Based on the average of years, I_R resulted in decreased
170 Fv/Fm when B ($I_0N_HB_0=0.66$; $I_RN_HB_0=0.53$) or N ($I_0N_0B_H=0.69$; $I_RN_0B_H=0.59$) or both
171 ($I_0N_0B_0=0.68$; $I_RN_0B_0=0.56$) were not consumed (Fig. 1.B), while Fv/Fm did not respond to I_R
172 when N and B were consumed together ($I_0N_HB_H=0.65$; $I_RN_HB_H=0.62$).

173 RWC was measured before (b) and after (a) irrigation. Based on the average of years, I_R
174 significantly reduced RWC_b ($I_0=70.6\%$; $I_R=65.6\%$; $LSD_{0.01}=3.8$), while it did not affect RWC_a .
175 The correlation of RWC with yield (GLY) was significant in both years only under restricted
176 irrigation (Table 1).

177 Based on the average of the years, the response of RWC_b to I_R was not significant when N
178 ($I_0N_H=69.2\%$; $I_RN_H=66.3\%$) or B ($I_0B_H=69.7\%$; $I_RB_H=66.4\%$) was consumed (Fig. 2.A, Fig. 2.B),
179 while I_R caused a significant decrease in RWC_b when N ($I_0N_0=72.0\%$; $I_RN_0=64.9\%$) or B

180 ($I_0B_0=71.5\%$; $I_RB_0=64.9\%$) was not consumed (Fig. 2.A, Fig. 2.B), leading to a significant $I \times N$
181 and $I \times B$ interactions in both years (Table 1).

182 The role of P in the response of RWC_b to I_R was contrary to the role of N and B. Based on the
183 average of years, I_R significantly reduced RWC_b when P was consumed ($I_0P_H=72.2\%$;
184 $I_RP_H=64.3\%$), while RWC_b did not respond to I_R when P was not consumed ($I_0P_0=69.1\%$;
185 $I_RP_0=67.0\%$), resulting in a significant $I \times P$ interaction on RWC_b in both years (Fig. 2.C and Table
186 1). $I \times P$ Interaction on leaf area per plant (LA) at R_6 was significant only in 2017 (Table 1). In
187 2017, When P was not consumed, I_R caused a 26.6% ($I_0P_0=0.15 \text{ m}^2 \text{ plant}^{-1}$; $I_RP_0=0.11 \text{ m}^2 \text{ plant}^{-1}$)
188 significant decrease in LA at R_6 , while LA did not respond to I_R when P was consumed
189 ($I_0P_0=0.14 \text{ m}^2 \text{ plant}^{-1}$; $I_RP_0=0.12 \text{ m}^2 \text{ plant}^{-1}$).

190 Among the $N \times D$ combinations, I_R reduced RWC_b only in N_0D_5 ($I_0N_0D_5=72.8\%$,
191 $I_RN_0D_5=63.0$), leading to a significant $I \times N \times D$ Interaction on RWC_b in both years (Table 1, Fig.
192 2.D).

193 Based on the average of years, I_R significantly decreased GLY ($I_0=2641 \text{ kg ha}^{-1}$, $I_R=1948$
194 kg ha^{-1} $LSD_{0.01}=3.6$). $I \times N$, $I \times B$ interactions on GLY was significant in both years (Table 1).
195 Based on the average of years, when N or B was not consumed, I_R caused a 34.1% ($I_0N_0=2437 \text{ kg}$
196 ha^{-1} ; $I_RN_0=1604 \text{ kg ha}^{-1}$) and 33.8% ($I_0B_0=2724 \text{ kg ha}^{-1}$; $I_RB_0=1809 \text{ kg ha}^{-1}$) significant decrease
197 in GLY, while GLY did not respond to I_R when N or B was consumed (Fig. 3.A, Fig. 3. B).

198 Based on the average of years, N consumption significantly increased GLY by 36.0%
199 ($N_0=2011 \text{ kg ha}^{-1}$, $N_H=2 \text{ kg ha}^{-1}$ $573 \text{ LSD}_{0.01}$). In 2018, GLY responded to N only in the low

200 plant density ($N_0D_5=1984 \text{ kg ha}^{-1}$, $N_HD_5=2705 \text{ kg ha}^{-1}$; $N_0D_H=2059 \text{ kg ha}^{-1}$, $N_HD_H=2430 \text{ kg ha}^{-1}$),
201 leading to a significant $N \times D$ Interaction on GLY in 2018.

202 Among the $N \times D$ combinations, I_R reduced GLY only in N_0D_5 ($I_0N_0D_5=2525 \text{ kg ha}^{-1}$,
203 $I_RN_0D_5=1453 \text{ kg ha}^{-1}$), leading to a significant $I \times N \times D$ Interaction on GLY in both years (Table 1,
204 Fig. 3.C). Among the $N \times B$ combinations, I_R reduced GLY only in N_0B_0 ($I_0N_0B_0=2503 \text{ kg ha}^{-1}$,
205 $I_RN_0B_0=1574 \text{ kg ha}^{-1}$), leading to a significant $I \times N \times B$ Interaction on GLY in both years (Table 1,
206 Fig. 3.D).

207

208 **DISCUSSION**

209 Reducing water consumption requires finding a way to prevent yield reduction under
210 restricted irrigation (I_R). I_R led to less GLY due to reduced F_v/F_m and RWC. Consumption of N
211 and P together prevented the photosynthetic efficiency (F_v/F_m) negative response to I_R (Fig.
212 1.A.). Shen and Li (2011) also reported that I_R impaired PS II function in wheat, and this effect
213 was significantly ameliorated by NP fertilizer but not N alone. PSB bacteria (B) was able to play
214 the role of P to reduce I_R effect on F_v/F_m , but not without N (Fig. 1.B.). N or B was able to
215 reduce the effect of I_R on RWC (Fig. 2.A. and Fig. 2.B.). This trend was also observed for GLY.
216 GLY did not respond to I_R when N and B were consumed together or alone (Fig. 3.A. and Fig.
217 3.B.). Researchers reported that increased resistance of photosynthesis to water stress at higher N
218 conditions (Singh et al. 2016) or in PSB incubated plants (Shintu and Jayaram, 2015) resulted
219 from improved RWC.

220 Jin et al (2015) reported that P supply under I_R conditions resulted in significantly greater
221 LA in pea. P had a reducing effect on RWC in I_R conditions (Fig. 2.C.), and its role in preventing
222 LA loss under I_R conditions in 2017 did not result in the improvement of GLY. The combination
223 of results to this point clearly shows that P either alone or in combination with N is not suitable
224 under I_R conditions, and its replacement with B is quite reasonable. The results indicate that P can
225 be eliminated under I_R conditions when N and B are used together. Ding et al. (2014) reported
226 that N application increased inorganic P uptake in soils with low P by improving the PSB
227 performance.

228 N increased GLY without increasing Fv/Fm and RWC. However, $I \times N \times D$ interaction on
229 RWC and GLY in both years (Fig. 2.D. and Fig. 3.C.), and the $N \times D$ interaction on GLY in 2018
230 was significant. This result showed that I_R reduced RWC and GLY in low density plots without
231 nitrogen consumption, but using N or higher plant density was enough to prevent this decline
232 (Fig. 2.D. and Fig. 3.C.) Researchers also found that plants treated with high N showed higher
233 RWC (Chang et al. 2016) and Fv/Fm (Abid et al. 2016) than low N treatment under I_R conditions.
234 Considering the necessity of simultaneous use of N and B to prevent Fv/Fm reduction under I_R
235 conditions and also the results of $I \times N \times B$ interaction on GLY (Fig. 3.D.), it does not seem that
236 some N is not totally eliminated under I_R conditions.

237 Application of each fertilizer alone or just increase plant density did not change RWC and
238 Fv/Fm. However, $I \times N \times P$ and $I \times N \times B$ interactions on Fv/Fm and also $I \times N$, $I \times B$ and $I \times N \times D$
239 interactions on RWC were significant. These results shows that the alleviated negative effect of

240 water shortage on GLY is attributed to fertilizer \times plant density synergic effect. Singh et al.
241 (2012) also reported that the potential effects of adopting high plant population with a minimum
242 recommended dose of NPK fertilizer management offer an excellent opportunity to increase crop
243 productivity in rainfed fields.

244 **CONCLUSIONS**

245 The study investigates the nitrogen \times PSB bacteria synergic effect on photosynthesis and
246 water relation of a crop under water stress conditions and different plant densities. I_R reduced
247 GLY from 2437 kg ha⁻¹ to 1604 kg ha⁻¹ when N and from 2724 kg ha⁻¹; to 1809 kg ha⁻¹) when B
248 was not consumed, while GLY did not respond to I_R when N or B was consumed together. In low
249 plant density and without N consumption, I_R reduced GLY from 2525 kg ha⁻¹ to 1453 kg ha⁻¹,
250 while GLY did not respond to I_R in other nitrogen \times plant density combinations. These results
251 conclude that phosphorus can be replaced with PSB bacteria under restricted irrigation
252 conditions, and the synergic interaction of nitrogen \times PSB-bacteria can strongly reduce the effect
253 of drought stress on cotton yield in high plant density.

254

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 321 **Table 1.** Separate ANOVA for 2017 and 2018 years, and Pearson coefficient correlations
 322 between Fv/Fm, Relative Water Content (RWC), and cotton yield (GLY) under moderate (I_0) and
 323 restricted irrigation (I_R).

2017				2018			
Pearson correlation							
Optimal Irrigation (I_0)							
	Fv/Fm	RWC	GLY		Fv/Fm	RWC	GLY
Fv/Fm	-	NS	NS	Fv/Fm	-	NS	NS
RWC	NS	-	NS	RWC	NS	-	NS
Restricted irrigation (I_R)							
Fv/Fm	-	NS	0.50 **	Fv/Fm	-	NS	0.57 **
RWC	NS	-	0.38 **	RWC	NS	-	0.42 **
ANOVA							
I	**	**	**	I	**	**	**
N	ns	ns	**	N	ns	ns	**
I×N	ns	**	ns	I×N	ns	**	**
N×D	ns	ns	ns	N×D	ns	ns	**
I×B	ns	**	**	I×B	ns	**	**
I×P	ns	**	ns	I×P	ns	**	ns
I×N×D	ns	**	**	I×N×D	ns	**	**
I×N×B	**	ns	**	I×N×B	**	ns	**
I×N×P	**	ns	ns	I×N×P	**	ns	ns
Leaf Area per Plant				Leaf Area per Plant			
I×P	**			I×P	NS		

349 I: Irrigation; N: Nitrogen; D: Density; B: PSB bacteria; P: Phosphorus;
 350 **, * and ns: significant at 0.01, 0.05 and non-significant, respectively.

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Figure1. Interaction of some experimental factors on Fv/Fm based on the average of years. I₀ and I_R: moderate and restricted irrigation, respectively. N₀ and N_H: without and with nitrogen consumption, respectively. P₀ and P_H: without and with Phosphorus consumption, respectively. B₀ and B_H: without and with PSB consumption, respectively.

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Figure. 2. Interaction of some experimental factors on RWC based on the average of the years. I₀ and I_R: moderate and restricted irrigation, respectively. N₀ and N_H: without and with nitrogen consumption, respectively. P₀ and P_H: without and with Phosphorus consumption, respectively. B₀ and B_H: without and with PSB consumption, respectively. D₀ and D_H: Low (5 plant m⁻²) and high (10 plants m⁻²) plant density, respectively.

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Figure 3. Interaction of some experimental factors on yield (GLY) based on the average of years. I₀ and I_R: moderate and restricted irrigation, respectively. N₀ and N_H: without and with nitrogen consumption, respectively. B₀ and B_H: without and with PSB consumption, respectively. D₀ and D_H: Low (5 plants m⁻²) and high (10 plant m⁻²) plant density, respectively.

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